

Bioengineering Lipid-based Synthetic Cells for Therapeutic Proteins Delivery

Sónia Siquenique^{1,2,3}; Shanny Ackerman⁴; Avi Schroeder⁴; Bruno Sarmiento^{1,2,5*}

¹ i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal

² INEB – Instituto de Engenharia Biomédica, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal

³ ICBAS–Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas Abel Salazar, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal

⁴ The Louis Family Laboratory for Targeted Drug Delivery and Personalized Medicine Technologies, Department of Chemical Engineering, Technion, Haifa, Israel

⁵ IUCS-CESPU – Instituto Universitário de Ciências da Saúde, Gandra, Portugal

* Correspondence: bruno.sarmiento@i3s.up.pt (B. Sarmiento)

Abstract

Synthetic cells (SCs) offer a promising approach for therapeutic protein delivery, combining principles from synthetic biology and drug delivery. Engineered to mimic natural cells, SCs provide biocompatibility and versatility, with precise control over their architecture and composition. Protein production is essential in living cells, and SCs aim to replicate this process using compartmentalized cell-free protein synthesis (CFPS) systems within lipid bilayers. Lipid bilayers serve as favored membranes in SC design due to their similarity to the biological cell membrane. Moreover, engineering lipidic membranes enable tissue-specific targeting and immune evasion, while stimulus-responsive SCs allow for triggered protein production and release. This review explores lipid-based SCs as platforms for therapeutic protein delivery, discussing their design principles, functional attributes, and translational challenges and potential.

Keywords: synthetic cells, cell-free protein synthesis, cell-free gene expression, therapeutic proteins

Lipid-based synthetic cell: an advanced platform for protein delivery

Synthetic cells (SCs) offer a promising strategy for therapeutic protein production and delivery by harnessing the principles of synthetic biology and drug delivery. SCs are engineered entities that mimic the structure and function of living cells offering unique advantages for therapeutic protein delivery due to their biocompatibility and versatility [1]. Moreover, bottom-up assembly techniques for SC production enable precise control over SC architecture and composition.

In living cells, protein production is a central process essential for carrying out a wide range of cellular functions. Mimicking this capability in SCs represents a significant challenge but also a promising opportunity for applications in biotechnology and biomedicine. The most commonly used strategy to enable protein production in SCs involves compartmentalizing **cell-free protein synthesis (CFPS)** (see glossary) systems within lipid bilayers [2]. CFPS is a promising method to generate recombinant proteins that can resolve the limitations of traditional cell-based methods. CFPS, initially employed by Nirenberg and Matthaei in the 1960s to decode the genetic blueprint [3], has been used for decades. Overall, the development of these CFPS systems has offered synthetic biologists a versatile technique that recapitulates the flow of genetic information from DNA and RNA to protein *in vitro* [4]. Furthermore, these cell-free systems offer multiple benefits, such as expressing multiple proteins and enzymes simultaneously at different levels by adjusting the concentrations of each DNA plasmid, paving the way for reconstructing genetically programmable artificial cells [5]. Moreover, they demonstrate a notable adaptability to high-throughput experiments and possess flexibility in incorporating additional molecular components for making more advanced artificial cell models.

The compartmentalization of CFPS systems inside membranes represents a promising platform to mimic the living cell function of protein production. The integration of CFPS within membranes allows the development of systems that can produce proteins in a controlled, cell-like environment. This integration enables localized and efficient protein synthesis, essential for applications such as targeted drug delivery. By encapsulating CFPS within membranes, researchers can replicate natural cellular processes, achieve precise control over protein expression, and explore innovative therapeutic and biotechnological solutions. Currently, the most favored system for SC membrane design is lipid bilayers due to their similarity to the biological cell membrane ensuring biocompatibility and making them suitable for medical and biotechnological applications [6]. Moreover, lipid bilayers present flexibility to incorporate various functional molecules that can facilitate tissue-specific targeting, promote the evasion from immune detection, and allow to program SCs to respond to external stimuli, enabling a triggered release of proteins in response to physiological cues [7, 8]. Leveraging the capacity of CFPS to produce functional therapeutic proteins, along with the advantageous features of lipid-based membranes, leads to the development of SCs as promising platforms for therapeutic protein production and delivery.

SCs hold immense potential for a wide range of therapeutic applications, including cancer therapy, regenerative medicine, and the treatment of genetic disorders. However, several challenges must be addressed to facilitate their clinical translation. This review paper aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the tunability and versatility of lipid-based SCs as platforms for the delivery of therapeutic proteins.

Moreover, explores the engineering principles underlying SC design, the functional attributes enabling protein production and delivery, and the translational potential of SC-based therapeutic protein delivery systems in various therapeutic applications (Figure 1, Key figure).

CFPS Systems and Therapeutic Protein Production

CFPS has been used as a powerful tool to accelerate the progress of synthetic biology. By using extracted cellular machinery, these systems bypass the complexities of living organisms, providing more control and predictability (Box 1). Early studies demonstrated that cell extracts could run *in vitro* with unexpectedly robust stability and high efficiency [3, 9-12]. Nowadays, these systems can produce functional proteins on an industrial scale [13] with diverse applications across multiple fields. In the therapeutic field, CFPS system has been used for generating a wide array of therapeutic protein products, including various antibodies [14-17], antimicrobial peptides [18-21], and vaccine antigens [14, 22-28] (Table 1) [29]. Since 2016, about 70% of all recombinant therapeutic proteins and monoclonal antibodies in the biopharmaceutical market have been produced from CHO cell lines [30-32]. The fast and affordable growth conditions of CHO cells and the potential to produce non-immunogenic antibodies with similar glycosylation patterns to those of human antibodies make these systems a top choice for recombinant therapeutic proteins [30]. However, the risk that many therapeutic proteins may not be accessible due to their potential to harm the producing host upon induction makes CFPS systems a preferred choice for therapeutic protein screening and production. Moreover, CFPS systems based on CHO cells retain most of the features of CHO cells while offering enhanced flexibility [33-35]. CFPS platforms streamline the high-throughput production of therapeutic proteins overcoming several drawbacks associated with their expression in cells offering enhanced flexibility. These cell-free systems present significant potential and open new avenues, particularly for the high-yield production of pharmaceutically relevant proteins and for the screening of new candidates as potent therapeutic proteins.

Bioengineering CFPS Systems for Stimuli-Responsive Production of Therapeutic Proteins

The integration of signal switches into CFPS platforms holds significant potential, particularly in healthcare applications. By harnessing these signals, researchers can enhance the functionality and versatility of genetic circuits engineered for various therapeutic purposes. Whether by triggering the production of therapeutic proteins or modulating cellular behavior, the introduction of signal switches expands the capabilities of CFPS systems, paving the way for more precise and efficient biomedical interventions. The potential of CFPS-based sensors to regulate protein expression in response to the microenvironment composition puts CFPS-incorporating SCs in that closely mimics living cells' capacity to sense and respond. The use of physical signals to regulate gene expression represents a promising avenue in biotechnology. Unlike chemical substances, physical signals often exhibit lower toxicity and fewer side effects, rendering them safer options for manipulating genetic pathways [36]. In that sense light can be used as a physical signal to regulate gene expression in cell-free systems. CFPS-based sensors have been exploited for the incorporation of light-responsive elements that can activate or inhibit the transcription or translation machinery when exposed to

specific wavelength. Jayaraman and colleagues demonstrated effective control of red fluorescent protein synthesis using blue light in a cell-free system [37]. This control was facilitated by a blue light-switchable bacterial transcription factor called EL222, which is part of the light-oxygen-voltage (LOV) domain protein family [38]. EL222 cannot bind to DNA in the absence of light, but upon exposure to light, it binds to DNA and initiates gene transcription [37]. This regulation mechanism is straightforward and involves only one regulatory protein [39]. On the other hand, Zhang and colleagues developed a blue light-regulated two-component system named YF1/FixJ that was incorporated into an *E. coli*-based cell-free system to control protein synthesis [40]. The YF1/FixJ system was an artificially modified *E. coli* blue light-sensing system based on the FixL/FixJ two-component system. YF1 is a fusion protein, which was obtained by linking the LOV blue light sensor domain of *Bacillus subtilis* YtvA to the FixL histidine kinase from *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. YF1 and FixJ form a new two-component system that responds to blue light and regulates protein expression in *E. coli* systems [40]. Another approach to control transcription and translation in cell-free systems with light is by the modification of DNA or RNA with photocages. Photocages are light-sensitive molecules that are attached to a bioactive molecule, inhibiting its activity. When exposed to a specific wavelength of light, the photocage undergoes a cleavage reaction, releasing the original molecule [41]. Smith and colleagues developed an approach for the light activation of CFPS by attaching photocaged biotin/monovalent streptavidin (mSA) to a T7 promoter sequence [42]. C6-amino-dT–modified bases are incorporated into T7 promoter sequence and react with a photocleavable 2-nitrobenzyl biotin. Subsequent binding of mSA to each biotin group creates a steric blockade that impedes T7 RNA polymerase from binding to the T7 promoter. However, when exposed to UV light, the 2-nitrobenzyl group was photocleaved, and mSA was liberated enabling gene expression [42, 43]. Recently, the authors also developed a system where transcription could be selectively turned ON with blue light and translation turned OFF with UV light. For that, they combined a blue-light activated DNA template with UV-controlled **antisense oligonucleotides** (ASOs) (see glossary) [44]. The authors attached orthogonal UV and blue photocaged biotins (nitrobenzyl and coumarin, respectively), and then mSA, to amino-C6-dTs positioned across ASOs, to tightly control gene knockdown in cell-free systems using light [44]. These bioengineering strategies enable the control of cell-free protein production by light improving the versatility, adaptability, and therapeutic applicability of CFPS-incorporating SCs. Light-controllable gene expression inside SCs opens new avenues to produce therapeutic proteins or enzymes at specific sites within the body, minimizing systemic side effects and enhancing the efficacy of the treatment. Moreover, it allows real-time regulation of protein synthesis, optimizing production efficiency which can lead to higher yields and improved quality of the biopharmaceuticals.

Magnetic force is another physical signal that can be used to regulate cell-free protein production. Finkler and colleagues described a simple method to control gene expression in CFPS using nanomagnetic beads [45]. They used magnetic beads coated with DNA of the gene of interest to trigger cell-free gene expression. The expression stopped when bead-bound DNA was removed, as well as transcribed mRNA by hybridization to bead-bound ssDNA [45]. The use of magnetic force to control cell-free gene expression remains poorly explored. However, represents a promising approach

for therapeutic applications as magnetic force possesses superior tissue penetration capabilities than light without causing global effects [36].

Temperature also serves as a promising signal for controlling cell-free gene expression. Various mechanisms, such as heat-shock protein promoters, thermo-sensitive repressors, and **RNA thermometers** (RNATs) (see glossary) are involved in triggering the transcription process in CFPS systems. Alterations in temperature affect the structure of these components, thereby influencing gene transcription [36]. Recently, Yang and colleagues used a temperature-sensitive variant of the bacteriophage λ repressor cI857 to develop a temperature-controlled CFPS system. The bacteriophage λ repressor cI857 is a well-known temperature-sensitive variant acting on tandem pR-pL operator-promoter, which effectively regulates genes cloned downstream. It inhibits gene expression when the temperature is lower than 37°C (usually 28–32°C) and inactivates the mutated suppressor when the temperature is above 37°C, allowing transcription to occur [46]. Bioengineering CFPS to trigger protein production when the temperature is close to the physiological temperature represents an opportunity to avoid the premature production of therapeutic proteins, minimizing the risk of protein degradation. Another approach to regulate cell-free gene expression using temperature is the incorporation of RNATs in the cell-free system. RNATs are temperature-responsive non-coding RNA sequences situated in the 5'-untranslated region of messenger RNA that regulate gene translation. These sequences form secondary structures and block ribosome binding sites (RBS) at low temperatures, inhibiting translation processes [47]. When temperature increases at a defined threshold, the RNAT loop unfolds and releases the RBS for subsequent gene expression. Jia and co-authors designed different temperature RNAT switches to regulate expression in PURE systems. They observed that at 37°C, RNAT inhibited PURE reaction from expressing red fluorescent protein ("off" state), and at 42°C, an increased expression could be observed ("on" state) [47]. Taking advantage of similar technologies and incorporating these temperature-responsive CFPS systems inside SCs, allows the development of dynamic platforms that can finely regulate therapeutic protein production according to temperature variations inside the body. Local body temperature can vary in response to ambient conditions and diseases in some cases. Increased body temperatures are normally observed due to fever, inflammation, or other diseases. For instance, in solid tumors, the temperature often differs from the baseline body temperature and compared to healthy tissues, may be elevated or reduced [48]. Moreover, temperature can be modulated by external stimuli like focused ultrasound, infrared light, and magnetic particle hyperthermia. In that sense, the administration of SCs capable to trigger protein production in response to specific temperatures would allow the *in situ* production of therapeutic proteins minimizing off-target effects and enhancing therapeutic efficacy. Moreover, the ability to finely tune the transcription process to be switched "on" or "off" based on alterations in temperature confers a dynamic adaptability of the system to physiological changes in the diseased microenvironment. This ensures that therapeutic proteins are synthesized in optimal dosages, avoiding under- or over-production, which can lead to ineffective treatment or adverse effects.

The therapeutic potential of SCs incorporating cell-free systems controlled by physical signals holds immense promise for revolutionizing biomedical applications. By integrating precise control mechanisms such as light, magnetic force, or temperature,

these SCs can be engineered to respond dynamically to their environment and produce therapeutic proteins or enzymes at specific sites within the body (Figure 2). Moreover, SCs incorporating bioengineered CFPS systems can create dynamic drug delivery systems that release therapeutic payloads in response to specific cues. This enables precise spatiotemporal control over drug release, minimizing off-target effects and enhancing therapeutic efficacy.

Bioengineering Lipid-based Synthetic Cell Membrane for Advanced Therapeutic Protein Delivery

CFPS compartmentalized inside lipidic vesicles has been established as one of the most popular and studied types of gene-expressing SCs [49]. These lipidic vesicles provide a protective and compartmentalized environment for CFPS reactions, closely mimicking the structure and function of natural cellular membranes. The lipid bilayer of the vesicles enables selective permeability, allowing for controlled exchange of substrates and products with the surrounding environment. Furthermore, lipidic vesicles offer a platform for the integration of additional components, such as membrane proteins and signalling molecules, enabling the construction of more complex and functional SCs.

Compartmentalization of CFPS systems inside lipid-based vesicles requires the optimization of several parameters on SC membrane design that can influence cell-free protein production inside SCs. Vesicle size is an important factor that affects compartmentalized protein synthesis. CFPS system comprises a high number of components that are detrimental for protein synthesis. As such, larger liposomes increase the probability of enclosing all necessary biochemical components, resulting in higher yields of protein production. **Giant unilamellar vesicles (GUVs)** (see glossary) with diameters of up to 10 μm represent a more promising platform for CFPS encapsulation when compared to unilamellar liposomes in the nanosize range (Box 2) [50, 51]. In that sense, lamellarity also affects protein production. Multilamellar vesicles are known to have a complex internal substructure presenting low entrapment capacity, leading to low levels of protein synthesis [52]. Tailoring these parameters on SC vesicles enables the optimization of protein synthesis rates and yields. Advances in lipid vesicle design hold promise for enhancing protein synthesis within SCs for diverse applications in biotechnology and biomedicine.

SCs are engineered to mimic the functionality of natural cells, providing precise control over cellular behaviour. The integration of sensory systems into their lipid membranes allows them to interact with and adapt to their surroundings in real-time. Furthermore, the incorporation of targeted delivery mechanisms enables precise navigation through complex biological environments to specific sites. These attributes enhance the adaptability of SCs, presenting the dynamic ability to synthesize active proteins and respond autonomously to environmental stimuli, mirroring key characteristics of living organisms.

Stimuli-Responsive Membranes

SC membranes can be engineered to incorporate structures that selectively enable the entry or exit of signalling molecules. This capacity brings the SC technology closer to the goal of mimicking living cells and their ability to sense and respond to the

microenvironment. A combination of cell-free sensing systems and membrane bioengineering allows the development of stimuli-responsive SCs, enabling an adaptation of these systems to a dynamic environment (Figure 3). This capability opens a myriad of possibilities for the targeted delivery of therapeutic proteins, where therapeutic proteins can be released only when and where they are needed most.

Bioengineering SC membrane for the incorporation of membrane proteins expands the versatility and the dynamic of the system. Incorporation of membrane proteins selectively enables the entry of signalling molecules which in turn can be used to regulate the synthesis and release of therapeutic proteins. Simple channels, such as the water-soluble pore α -hemolysin (α HL) have been explored in stimuli-responsive SCs to control the entry or release of small substances [19, 53, 54]. α HL is a member of a large family of pore-forming toxins from *Staphylococcus aureus*, the cholesterol-dependent cytolysin family [53]. The pore-forming protein α HL is inserted into the lipid bilayer, enabling the passage of molecules smaller than 3 kDa through the liposomal membrane, while keeping larger macromolecules confined within the SC. Interestingly, Adamala and colleagues demonstrated that adjusting the concentration of α HL DNA within synthetic vesicles allows for modulation of α HL expression, resulting in vesicles exhibiting varying permeability levels [55]. Furthermore, additional studies have indicated that protein integration is influenced by membrane composition. Specifically, α HL insertion requires the presence of PC head groups at the membrane interface [56], along with the presence of cholesterol within the membrane [57]. Expression and integration of α HL into SC membrane can be achieved by encapsulating CFPS systems inside lipidic membranes in combination with a DNA template encoding to α HL membrane protein [53]. The possibility of combining different DNA templates in CFPS systems enables the co-translational expression of the therapeutic protein and the pore-forming protein. Moreover, the use of stimuli-responsive CFPS systems enables a signal-dependent expression of α HL allowing precise control over SC permeability. For instance, Dwidar and colleagues designed a histamine-responsive programmable artificial cell where the addition of histamine activated the cell-free expression of α HL and its incorporation within the liposome membrane [54]. In therapeutics, this type of approach expands the opportunity to precisely control the release of the therapeutic protein. The incorporation of membrane channels in response to a specific signal from the microenvironment enables precise control over SC membrane permeability which in turn helps to achieve a controlled release kinetics of the therapeutic protein and minimizes systemic side effects.

The incorporation of membrane proteins in SC membrane enhances the SC's ability to sense and respond to the microenvironment facilitating communication with natural cells and between different populations of SCs [55]. For instance, Tang and coworkers engineered lipid-based SCs to trigger an enzymatic cascade reaction in a distinct population of SCs [58]. They observed that introducing a lipid-permeable small molecule transcription inducer promoted intravesicular α HL expression, leading to the formation of membrane pores, and enabling glucose release from the vesicle. Consequently, released glucose triggered an enzymatic cascade on the recipient artificial cell generating a fluorescent output. The incorporation of specific carrier proteins into SC membrane increases the dynamic ability to release therapeutic proteins in response to environmental stimuli, mirroring key characteristics of living organisms. Chen and coworkers developed SCs with the ability to release insulin in response to high glucose

levels, by incorporating glucose transporter 2 (GLUT2) in the GUVs membrane [59]. These stimuli-responsive SCs were constructed by encapsulating glucose oxidase and insulin-encapsulating liposomes inside GUVs. Upon glucose intake, oxidation of glucose oxidase occurred, leading to a decrease in pH inside the GUVs. This pH change caused the peptides attached to the insulin-loaded liposomes to interact with a second set of peptides tethered to the inner surface of the GUV, promoting fusion between the liposomes and the GUV membrane, thereby releasing the insulin. These glucose-responsive SCs were dispersed within a hydrogel-forming solution and then injected subcutaneously into streptozotocin-induced type 1 diabetic mice. This system successfully maintained normal glucose levels in the treated mice for up to five days. This study shows the therapeutic potential of SCs and their ability to sense and respond from the microenvironment. For therapeutic applications, communication between SCs and natural cells can create these synergistic effects, enhancing the overall therapeutic impact. This SC capacity to stimulate natural cells can be explored in several diseases, namely tissue regeneration, tumors, or boosting immune responses against pathogens. For instance, to support tissue regeneration SCs can be designed to produce growth factors, cytokines, and other signalling molecules essential for tissue repair and regeneration. These SCs can mimic natural cellular responses, promoting the healing of damaged tissues and organs.

Engineering SC to express protein products in response to mechanical force has also been explored through the incorporation of mechanically sensitive membrane proteins into SC membrane [60]. The *E. coli* mechanosensitive channel of large conductance (MscL) is an osmotically activated release valve derived from bacteria that can be integrated into artificial cell membranes. This protein can be expressed by *E. coli* extract-based CFPS, forming a mechanosensitive gate that responds to membrane stretching. In SCs, MscL has been observed to open, creating a 3-nm pore through which small molecule inducers can enter the interior and trigger additional encapsulated CFPS reactions. This response has been demonstrated under conditions of osmotic stress and enzymatically induced alterations in lateral membrane pressure [60]. In the human body, the mechanical changes in the diseased microenvironment, such as pressure changes in tumors or inflamed tissues can serve as stimuli for the release of therapeutics from mechanosensitive SCs. Upon detecting such changes, these channels can open, releasing the encapsulated therapeutic proteins in a controlled manner. This smart delivery system ensures that the drugs are released in response to real-time physiological conditions.

Bioengineering SC membrane to sense pH variations in the extracellular environment represents also a promising stimuli-responsive platform for therapeutic protein delivery [61, 62]. A possible approach is the incorporation of CHEMS, a carboxylated lipid between DOPE molecules. CHEMS promotes the formation of more stable liposomes and confers pH-responsiveness properties to the vesicle. When the carboxyl group of CHEMS becomes protonated, its stabilizing properties decrease. In an acidic environment, these liposomes destabilize, transforming into inverted hexagonal micelles and releasing their encapsulated contents [63]. This approach enables the release of high payloads of CFPS-produced protein on a target site predictably and responsively. pH-responsive SCs might have relevant applicability to cancer therapy by leveraging the acidic surroundings outside tumor cells as a potential stimulus for the release of antitumor toxins produced inside SCs.

Bioengineering SC membrane enables the development of stimuli-responsive membranes which offer opportunities for the on-demand release of therapeutic payloads in response to specific disease biomarkers or stimuli from the diseased microenvironment. This level of control enables precise dosing regimens and minimizes the risk of systemic toxicity. Additionally, stimuli-responsive membranes can be integrated with other functionalities, such as molecular sensors or targeting ligands, to further enhance their therapeutic capabilities.

Surface functionalization and target delivery

Surface modification of artificial cells can improve payload delivery conferring specific functionalities such as targeting ligands, stealth coatings, and stimuli-responsive moieties [64]. Surface functionalization with targeting ligands allows SCs to selectively recognize and bind to specific receptors expressed on target cells or tissues. Surface functionalization of liposomal SCs can be achieved through pre-functionalization of the lipids forming the outer membrane. These strategies improve the probability that moieties are localized mainly on the liposomal outer surface, thus resulting in more inner space available for CFPS encapsulation and protein synthesis [62].

Membrane functionalization with PEG confers important features for *in vivo* applications of SCs, such as stealth coating and consequently improved circulation time [7, 8]. PEG is a polymer that is usually conjugated to lipid headgroups to increase stability and decrease permeability. Moreover, this polymer contains active functional groups capable of attaching to different functional sites of specific moieties for a target delivery, representing a stable and versatile linker molecule for SC functionalization with specific ligands. Dahore and colleagues incorporated DSPE-PEG-Maleimide in SCs composition as a bioconjugation strategy to attach peptide-major histocompatibility complexes (pMHC) molecules onto SCs surface and promote T cell binding and activation [65]. To couple pMHC to the exposed maleimide groups, the authors reacted liposomes with pMHC refolded using heavy chains engineered with a C-terminal cysteine, to introduce a free thiol group that could be selectively reduced for bioconjugation [65]. Functionalized SCs selectively bonded T cells in an antigen-specific manner. This strategy enables functionalization of the SC surface with a variety of targeting ligands, biomolecules, peptides, antibodies, etc. SC surface functionalization can enhance their properties or introduce new features to enable targeting with accuracy. For instance, SC membrane can be surface functionalized with adhesion molecules to promote cell-to-cell communication and cell-specific targeting. Chakraborty and colleagues, surface-functionalized two different populations of SCs with adhesion molecules which bound to each other under blue light and dissociated from each other in the dark. The proteins iLID and Nano were anchored onto the outer membrane of two distinct populations of GUVs by binding their His-tags to the Ni²⁺-nitrilotriacetic acid head group of the lipid [66]. A two-way communication between the surface-modified SCs was notable when compared to non-functionalized vesicles. Functionalization with adhesion molecules and other biomolecules can enhance interactions between SCs and target cells. This can facilitate more effective delivery and uptake of therapeutic proteins by the target cells.

Besides relatively unexplored in SC therapy, membrane functionalization strategies to control SCs spatially and temporally may expand the possibilities to tailor application-specific platforms. Functionalizing the SC membrane with specific ligands can direct the

cells to particular tissues or regions within the body. This spatial precision ensures that the therapeutic effects are localized to the target area, minimizing off-target effects and maximizing therapeutic efficacy.

Synthetic Cells and Therapeutic Proteins Production

The applicability of SCs to produce and deliver therapeutic proteins represents a highly promising prospect for applications in biotechnology and biomedicine. However, research in this field is still recent and poorly explored (Table 2).

In 2018, Krinsky and colleagues pioneered SC therapy by demonstrating that lipid vesicles containing CFPS could be used to synthesize anti-cancer proteins inside tumors [67]. In this work, the authors showed that SCs producing *Pseudomonas* exotoxin A killed most cancer cells in culture and caused robust apoptosis when injected into 4T1 tumors in mice. On-site expression, extended-release, and slower diffusion of the anticancer protein from the artificial cells were found to show better sensitivity to tumor cells compared with purified protein injection. Based on the same technology, genetically encoded SCs were constructed to secrete a recombinant human basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) to trigger the physiological process of neovascularization in mice [68]. The authors observed that local integration of FGF-producing SCs in mice for prolonged periods induced the recruitment of newly formed blood vessels. Toparlak and coworkers also developed a lipid-based SC system and demonstrated effective communication between gene-expressing SCs with engineered human embryonic kidney cells and murine neural stem cells (Duhan Toparlak et al., 2020). Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) is a neurotropic factor that is crucial in promoting the survival, growth, and differentiation of neurons in the nervous system. The authors engineered SCs to co-translationally express BDNF and perfringolysin O (PFO) which assembled into oligomeric pores of diameter around 25 nm allowing the BDNF release [8]. SCs were capable of chemically communicating with neurons and to promote the differentiation of neural stem cells. It was observed that BDNF-secreting SCs could influence the differentiation and maturation of mouse embryonic stem cell-derived neural stem cells [8]. These examples showcase the potential of SCs to produce active therapeutic proteins that directly influence the behavior of nearby living cells and cooperate through cascading reactions.

SCs hold immense potential for producing and delivering therapeutic proteins, yet this field of research remains relatively unexplored. Research on the applicability of CFPS bulk reactions for therapeutic protein production is vast and growing and industrial production has already been explored [69]. However, translating this CFPS potential into membrane-bound systems is still in the early stages. The entrapment of all the necessary CFPS components for protein production inside vesicles remains one of the main challenges that result in lower protein production yield compared to CFPS bulk reactions [67]. Continued research efforts are needed to optimize CFPS technology inside membranes to explore its promising potential for applications in biotechnology and biomedicine. The capability for membrane engineering would enable tissue-specific targeting, evasion from immune detection, and the capacity to respond to external stimuli enabling a triggered release of therapeutic proteins in response to physiological cues. These properties confer to SCs for a wide range of therapeutic applications.

Concluding remarks

SCs offer immense potential for therapeutic protein production and delivery. By mimicking the structure and function of natural cells, SCs provide unique advantages such as biocompatibility, versatility, and precise control over architecture, composition, and activity. Encapsulating CFPS systems within lipid bilayers has emerged as a prominent strategy for protein production in SCs, overcoming the limitations of traditional cell-based methods. SCs bring distinct advantages over traditional cell-based therapies, streamlining regulatory pathways and offering greater control over safety and efficacy assessments. The use of CFPS systems offers versatile and adaptable platforms, capable of expressing multiple proteins simultaneously and facilitating the construction of genetically programmable artificial cells. Additionally, the incorporation of non-canonical amino acids (ncAAs) into proteins through CFPS systems enables the creation of proteins with novel physicochemical properties and biological functions. Lipid bilayers, due to their similarity to biological membranes, are favored as membrane materials for SCs, enabling efficient encapsulation and protection of therapeutic proteins. Moreover, engineered membrane properties and surface modifications enable the triggered release of therapeutic payloads and tissue-specific targeting.

Nevertheless, several challenges and limitations must be addressed to realize the full potential of this innovative approach (see Outstanding Questions). Long-term stability represents one of the main challenges. Maintaining SC stability and protein production over extended periods is critical for therapeutic efficacy. Addressing stability and durability challenges, including membrane degradation and long-term activity, is essential for long-term therapeutic success. *de novo* synthesis of membrane phospholipids from internal pathways might represent an approach to repair membrane degradation. Recently, Eto and colleagues described a cell-free phospholipid synthesis system that combines fatty acid synthesis and a cell-free gene expression system synthesizing acyltransferases for self-synthesis of membrane phospholipids [70]. This type of approach might be applicable to enhance lipid vesicle durability. Also, the long-term activity of CFPS systems relies on the steady-state supply of ATP which is a limiting factor. Research efforts have been already applied to contour that limitation by engineering the CFPS components to form ATP, generate electrochemical ion gradients, and achieve energy homeostasis [71]. Another challenge is the control over the release of the therapeutic protein. Achieving controlled release kinetics of therapeutic proteins from SCs is crucial for maintaining therapeutic concentrations over time. Fine-tuning release kinetics to match therapeutic needs while avoiding premature release or protein degradation presents a delicate balance. Bioengineering lipidic membranes enhances the adaptability of SCs, presenting the dynamic ability to release active proteins in response to environmental stimuli, mirroring key characteristics of living organisms. Moreover, bioengineering CFPS for stimuli-responsive gene expression allows dynamic control over SC's activity by triggering or stopping the production of therapeutic proteins [44], expanding the capabilities of CFPS systems and paving the way for more precise and efficient biomedical interventions. The *in vivo* application of SCs also faces several challenges. One main challenge is related to vesicle size. Larger vesicles can increase the probability of entrapping all the CFPS constituents, however, their size may also affect their efficacy and biodistribution *in vivo*. Small liposomes, with a size of less than 200 nm show improved circulation and residence time in the bloodstream and significant accumulation within tumor cells [72]. However, entrapping CFPS to allow

protein synthesis inside small liposomes is very challenging. A possible approach to explore is the use of spontaneously formed solute-filled phospholipid giant vesicles and their subsequent fragmentation into several smaller vesicles [73]. Fanti and colleagues showed solute retention inside POPC vesicles during vesicle fragmentation by mechanical extrusion. Using similar technology, the retention of CFPS components inside extruded vesicles could be explored for the preparation of smaller-sized SCs. Another challenge regarding *in vivo* applications of SCs is immunogenicity. SCs may elicit immune responses or induce toxicity *in vivo*. Understanding and mitigating potential immunogenic and toxic effects through rigorous preclinical evaluation is essential for ensuring patient safety. Moreover, achieving scalability in the production of SCs is another significant milestone. Developing scalable production processes that maintain the integrity and functionality of CFPS-encapsulating lipidic vesicles is essential for their translation into clinical applications. We envisioned that the large-scale production of protein-producing SCs using microfluidic platforms would allow for precise control over SC assembly, maintaining consistency in SC size, membrane integrity, and encapsulated CFPS components across large-scale production batches which is crucial for reproducibility and reliability in protein synthesis.

In conclusion, significant work remains to fully achieve the therapeutic potential of SCs. Research efforts concerning SC stability and durability are critical for the advancement of these platforms for therapeutic applications. Moreover, optimizing SC size to maximize circulation time and biodistribution *in vivo* is essential. These optimizations are crucial for improving therapeutic outcomes and ensuring the clinical viability of SC-based therapies. Despite the current limitations, lipid-based SCs hold promise for therapeutic protein delivery, with several future perspectives driving their advancement. Advanced engineering can lead to SCs with enhanced functionality and performance, while biomimetic design principles can further enhance their capabilities. Additionally, engineering SCs to dynamically sense and respond to the microenvironment can unlock new therapeutic possibilities.

Author contribution

Sónia Siquenique: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft. Shanny Ackerman: Investigation, Writing – review & editing. Avi Schroeder: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. Bruno Sarmento: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Box 1- A closer look into CFPS systems

In DNA-dependent protein synthesis within CFPS systems, molecular components essential for transcription and translation are extracted from living cells. Commonly used crude extracts are either from prokaryotic hosts such as *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) cells [74, 75]; or from eukaryotic hosts such as wheat germ [76], insect cells [77], rabbit reticulocyte [78], chinese hamster ovary (CHO) and human cell lines [79]. Systems of purified recombinant elements (PURE) are also commercially available [80]. CFPS activity relies on external supplies of energy sources, amino acids, nucleotides, salts, crowding agents, and other essential molecules for protein production. Several protocols and recipes have been optimized for CFPS supplementation [21, 31]. The presence of phosphate donors that allow ATP regeneration is essential to provide chemical energy for the translation process, namely for aminoacylation of tRNAs and peptide bond formation. However, ATP supply is a major limiting factor in the long-term activity of CFPS [46-48] and it represents the main component that increases the overall cost of CFPS explaining the urge for cheaper sources of energy for cell-free reactions. Phosphoenolpyruvate, creatine phosphate, and acetyl phosphate are the most used phosphate donors in CFPS reactions [49]. However, the use of phosphate donors as energy sources causes the accumulation of inorganic phosphate (iP) in the system which has been shown to have a negative impact on CFPS reaction [81]. To avoid that, intermediates in the glycolytic pathway such as pyruvate, glucose-6-phosphate, and even glucose have been used to regenerate ATP instead of high-energy phosphate-containing substrates without causing iP accumulation [82]. 3-phosphoglycerate (3-PGA), a glycolytic molecule represents a promising energy source for CFPS as it seems less susceptible to breakdown by enzymes within the *E. coli* system used for CFPS. This allows for its gradual conversion into another energy source (PEP) through glycolysis, enabling sustained protein synthesis and ultimately higher protein yields [82]. Another important factor in the composition of CFPS systems is the presence of molecular crowding agents. The interior of biological cells is characterized by molecular crowding, a condition that naturally occurs and can impact cellular properties by reducing diffusion rates and promoting increased binding rates of macromolecules. Artificial cellular systems present a lower density of biomolecules than living cells. In CFPS reactions the addition of molecular crowding agents, such as polyethylene glycol (PEG) or dextran, emulates that environment increasing CFPS performance [83]. These molecules are often utilized as non-reactive agents that emulate the crowded interior of cells, without interacting with the systems of interest [84].

Box 2- Preparation method for synthetic cell membranes

GUVs are often prepared using the droplet transfer method (also called the inverted emulsion method) which is the most used procedure for CFPS entrapment inside a phospholipid bilayer. A water-in-oil (w/o) emulsion is first formed, allowing the formation of an inverted micelle surrounding an aqueous solution containing CFPS components [85]. The w/o droplets are typically created by simple manual or mechanical emulsification; therefore, they generally have a broad size distribution. Centrifugation steps allow w/o droplets to pass through a lipidic interface, with which phospholipid monolayer interacts to form the second layer of lipids, forming the bilayer membrane of the vesicle. To ensure the transition through the lipidic interface and the formation of the bilayer particles, isotonic solutions with different densities are added to the aqueous inner solution and the outer phase of the biphasic solution. This method results in high encapsulation efficacy and does not require the use of specialized equipment, making the procedure quite simple to reproduce. Particle diameter is usually around 1-20 μm [86]. One of the disadvantages of this method is the content of excess oil, which can be challenging to remove. In contrast, classical thin lipid film hydration offers an alternative, as it is a process that enhances the production of oil-free GUVs even at low temperatures and physiological salt concentrations [50]. However, thin lipid film hydration typically leads to low encapsulation efficiency and produces multilamellar vesicles of varying sizes, which poses a limitation [50]. More sophisticated techniques have been exploited for gene-expressing vesicle production such as microfluidics [87]. Droplet-based microfluidics offers the advantage of generating more homogeneous populations of vesicles compared to other conventional techniques. Due to the ability of microfluidics to manipulate fluids, the aqueous phase containing CFPS is encapsulated and turned into hundreds and thousands of droplets of uniform size [88].

Table 1. Therapeutic proteins produced through CFPS systems. ^a

Protein	Cell extract	Application	References
B-cell lymphoma Id	<i>E. coli</i>	β -cell lymphoma	[23, 28]
GM-CSF			
αCD19-Id	<i>E. coli</i>	β -cell lymphoma	[27]
Hemagglutinin	<i>E. coli</i>	Influenza	[89]
Streptolysin O toxoid	<i>E. coli</i>	Group A streptococcal infection	[24]
Crisantaspase	<i>E. coli</i>	Cancer therapy	[90]
Insulin-like growth factor I	<i>E. coli</i>	Central nervous system therapy	[91]
Truncated Pfs230	Wheat germ	Malaria	[92]
Streptokinase	Hela and CHO cell lines	Thrombolytic therapy	[93]
Chlamydia major outer-membrane protein	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Chlamydia</i> vaccine	[94]
Heavy-chain fragment of botulinum toxins A, B, and E	<i>E. coli</i>	Botulism vaccine	[95]
Plasmodium rhoptry proteins	HeLa/wheat germ	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>	[79, 96]
Malaria antigen, PfMSA180	Wheat germ	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>	[26]
Malaria antigen, Pfs25-GPI	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>	[17]
Hepatitis B core protein	<i>E. coli</i>	Hepatitis B virus	[25]
human parainfluenza virus type 3 hemagglutinin-neuraminidase	Wheat germ	Human parainfluenza virus 3	[97]
scFv; Fab antibody fragments; IgG 1	<i>E. coli</i>	Vaccines	[16, 69, 98-101]
scFv; mAbs; IgG1	CHO cell line	Vaccines	[33-35, 102]

^a Abbreviations: CHO, chinese hamster ovary; Fab, fragment antigen-binding region; GM-CSF, granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF); IgG1, immunoglobulin 1; mAB, monoclonal antibody; scFv, single-chain fragment variable.

Table 2. List of lipid-based synthetic cells producing therapeutic proteins.^b

Protein	Cell extract	Material	Method	Application	References
Pseudomonas exotoxin A	<i>E. coli</i>	POPC/Chol	Water-in-oil transfer method	Anti-cancer therapy	[67]
basic fibroblast growth factor	<i>E. coli</i>	POPC/Chol POPC/DOPC /Chol EPC:Chol	Water-in-oil transfer method	Production of proangiogenic factors to trigger neovascularization	[68]
Brain-derived neurotrophic factor	<i>E. coli</i>	POPC/Chol/ DSPE-PEG	Water-in-oil transfer method	Induce the differentiation of neural stem cells	[8]

^b Abbreviations: Chol, cholesterol; DOPC, 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (lipid); DSPE-PEG, 1,2-distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine-N- (polyethylene glycol (lipid); EPC, egg-phosphatidylcholine (lipid); POPC, 1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-glycero-3-phosphocholine (lipid).

Figure 1. Key figure. Schematic overview of the bioengineering principles underlying SC design and the potential for therapeutic protein production and delivery. Image created with Biorender.com.

Figure 2. Bioengineering CFPS for stimuli-responsive production of therapeutic proteins inside the body. (1) The CFPS system can be engineered to activate or inhibit

transcription and translation processes in response to a specific stimulus, such as light, temperature variations, magnetic force, etc. Additionally, these systems can be designed to express therapeutic proteins, including vaccine-antigens, antimicrobial peptides, toxins, hormones, enzymes, etc. (2) Compartmentalization of this stimuli-responsive CFPS inside lipid-based vesicles enables the production of therapeutic proteins within synthetic cells (SCs). (3) Administration of those SCs inside the human body allows the *in situ* production of the therapeutic protein in response to a specific stimulus minimizing systemic side effects and enhancing the efficacy of the treatment. Image created with Biorender.com.

Figure 3. Possible application of temperature-responsive SCs in cancer therapy. Bioengineered SCs represent promising platforms for therapeutic protein production and delivery in various diseases. For example, intratumoral injection of temperature-responsive SCs (TSCs) and subsequent heat of the tumor via focused ultrasound could allow the *in situ* production and release of anticancer proteins. TSCs can be constructed by incorporating specific RNA thermometers that can inhibit cell-free gene expression at physiological temperature ($\sim 37^{\circ}\text{C}$) and activate it at higher temperature ($\sim 42^{\circ}\text{C}$). Moreover, SCs can be engineered to co-translationally express an anticancer protein and a membrane protein to enable the release of the therapeutic protein inside the tumor tissue. This system would allow the anticancer drug to diffuse into the surrounding tumor tissue. Image created with Biorender.com.

Glossary

Antisense oligonucleotides

short DNA sequences that can selectively degrade a target mRNA in the presence of a ribonuclease

Cell-free protein synthesis

a system to produce proteins *in vitro*. All the components needed for transcription and translation processes are extracted from living cells and supplemented with building blocks and energy molecules to allow the synthesis of proteins based on a DNA template outside of a living organism.

Giant unilamellar vesicles

micro-sized lipid vesicles which are usually employed for synthetic cell design due to their similarity with living cell membrane.

RNA thermometers

short non-coding RNA sequences situated in the 5'-untranslated region of messenger RNA that regulate gene translation.

Synthetic cell

artificially created structures designed to mimic the structure and function of natural cells. They are engineered entities developed through synthetic biology techniques, offering unique capabilities for various applications in biotechnology and medicine.

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